
The Role of Bawaslu in the Neutrality of the Civil Service in Regional Elections in Bone Regency (Siyasah Syar'iyah Analysis)

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Abstract:

This thesis discusses the role of Bawaslu in maintaining the neutrality of the State Civil Apparatus (ASN) in regional elections in Bone Regency from the perspective of Siyasah Syar'iyah. This study focuses on three main issues, namely: (1) The strategies implemented by Bawaslu in maintaining the neutrality of ASN. (2) The view of Siyasah Syar'iyah on the neutrality of ASN in the context of supervision carried out by Bawaslu Bone Regency. This study uses a qualitative approach with descriptive analysis methods. The approaches used are theological-normative (sharia) and juridical-sociological. Data were collected from various sources such as Bawaslu Bone Regency, the Subdistrict Supervisory Committee (Panwascam), election observers, political parties, and community leaders. Data collection techniques included observation, interviews, and documentation, which were analyzed through the stages of data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. The results of the study show that: (1) Bawaslu's strategy in maintaining the neutrality of ASN is carried out through two main approaches, namely prevention and supervision. Prevention is carried out through socialization, distribution of appeal letters, and the use of social media, while supervision is carried out directly in the field and on the use of state or village facilities. (2) From the perspective of Siyasah Syar'iyah, violations of neutrality by ASN are contrary to the principle of justice, which is one of the main pillars of Islamic government. Such violations not only cause harm to society but also violate the oath of office, which, according to Islamic law, must be obeyed. The implications of this study emphasize the importance of applying political ethics within the framework of Siyasah Syar'iyah as a normative basis for maintaining the neutrality of civil servants. The government and Bawaslu are expected to increase transparency and accountability in the process of supervision and law enforcement by providing clear and detailed reports on each violation and its follow-up. This is important to strengthen public trust in the democratic process and the integrity of elections.

Keywords: Role of Bawaslu, Civil Servants, Siyasah Syar'iyah Analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Elections are a means of exercising people's sovereignty, conducted directly, publicly, freely, confidentially, honestly, and fairly in the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution. Elections are held to elect the President and Vice

President, the DPR, the DPD, and the DPRD. Meanwhile, regional elections are a means of exercising people's sovereignty to elect regional heads at the provincial and regency/city levels. Elections and regional elections in Indonesia are held directly every five years. Several institutions are entrusted with organizing elections and regional elections in Indonesia. These institutions are the General Election Commission (KPU) as the technical organizer of the elections, the Election Organizers Honorary Council (DKPP) as the election ethics council, and the Election Supervisory Agency (Bawaslu) as the election supervisory agency. (Susilo Prabowoadi & Afandi, 2020)

The neutrality of the State Civil Apparatus (ASN) is one of the crucial issues that has received a lot of attention in the implementation of the 2019 and 2024 regional elections because there is a lot of evidence that many civil servants are not neutral. The principles of civil service neutrality are regulated in the KASN code of ethics and code of conduct. This code of ethics is important for realizing a professional civil service, not only in terms of competence but also in terms of behavior in carrying out duties.

In 2014, to realize bureaucratic reform, the government issued Law Number 5 of 2014 concerning the Civil Service. This law explains and reaffirms the neutrality of civil servants (PNS) as bureaucrats who are part of the state. In fact, civil servants are no longer referred to as PNS but as civil servants, which consist of PNS and PPPK (government employees with work agreements). Article 9 paragraph (2) of the Civil Service Law states that: "civil servants must be free from the influence and intervention of all groups and political parties.¹ The issuance of the State Civil Apparatus Law, which regulates the principle of neutrality, can result in a state civil apparatus that is free from public intervention. In the bureaucratic world, the state civil apparatus is often used as a political machine. The neutrality of the State Civil Apparatus (ASN) is very important in ensuring that government institutions operate fairly and without bias. The prohibition of voting rights for ASN is regulated to support neutrality. However, this policy faces various legal challenges that need to be examined. If we look closely at Article 28 J paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution, it states that "in exercising their rights and freedoms, everyone must comply with restrictions established by law with the aim of guaranteeing recognition and respect for the rights and freedoms of others and to meet fair demands in accordance with moral considerations, religious values, security, and public order in a democratic society." This article illustrates that, ideally, rights and freedoms are not absolute. This means that even though a person has rights, there will be restrictions imposed by law with the intention that these rights do not harm the rights of others. These restrictions are necessary to maintain a balance between individual rights and the interests of society. (Luhukay, 2024)

The principle of neutrality based on Law Number 5 of 2014 is that every civil servant must not be influenced by any form of pressure and must not take sides with anyone's interests.

¹ Article 9 paragraph (2), Law Number 5 of 2014 concerning State Civil Apparatus.

Neutrality can also be interpreted as not taking sides with anything. In this context, neutrality is defined as civil servants not being involved or directly participating in and campaigning for regional head elections, general elections, and presidential elections, either actively or passively.

The issue of civil service neutrality is undeniably unresolved. The government has established various regulations to limit civil servants' involvement in practical political activities in order to strengthen neutrality. However, every regional election is always marred by reports of neutrality violations by civil servants. Based on historical facts, the vulnerability of civil servants in practical politics is influenced by their involvement in supporting one of the legislative candidate pairs or becoming part of the campaign team for a legislative candidate pair in exchange for the promise of a promotion. This further damages the image of the government due to the development of an unprofessional and biased work system that disregards the principle of neutrality. (Sudrajat et al., 2014)

In the implementation of regional head elections in several regions in Indonesia, the position of the civil service is still considered quite respectable and influential. In such a position, placing civil servants in a strategic position becomes a competition among candidates for regional head, as they believe that one civil servant can attract 5 to 10 people or even more. It is this kind of condition that is suspected to be a vulnerable point for civil servants to not be neutral.

The involvement of civil servants in politics is certainly not the first time it has occurred in regional head elections. Civil servants hold quite strategic positions. Meanwhile, in Islam, a neutral employee must be trustworthy, fair, impartial, and not engage in fraud. Injustice will only result in damage, where the wrong person is given authority, while the right person is accused of being a troublemaker. Injustice will further accelerate chaos, commotion, and destruction if it is carried out by a leader or ruler, while no one provides a counterbalance of opinion. (Saifuddin, 2018)

Based on the background of the problem above, the author was motivated to conduct more in-depth research with the title *The Role of Bawaslu in the Neutrality of the Civil Service in Regional Head Elections in Bone Regency (Siyasah Syar'iyah Analysis)*.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research is qualitative in nature, with data collection carried out through several main techniques, namely observation, interviews, and documentation. The observation technique was used to observe the objects or behaviors of participants directly. This observation could be carried out in a participatory manner, where the researcher was involved in the activities being observed, or in a non-participatory manner, where the researcher was only an observer. In this study, the researcher used non-participatory observation techniques, observing the community and paying attention to matters related to the neutrality of civil servants. In addition to observation, interview techniques were also used to explore information in depth

through open-ended questions to relevant sources who understood the election conditions in Bone Regency, such as members of the Election Supervisory Agency (Bawaslu), the Election Monitoring Agency (Panwasca), election observers, and community leaders. These interviews aimed to obtain more comprehensive and in-depth information. Documentation techniques were also applied to supplement the data obtained through observation and interviews. This documentation included searching for data in the form of documents, photos, transcripts, and reports relevant to the research topic to reinforce the results of the study.

The research instruments used included the researchers themselves as the main instrument, as well as tools such as interview guidelines, writing instruments, audio recordings via mobile phones, and cameras to document field activities. In data processing and analysis, the researchers applied three stages, namely data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. Data reduction was carried out to simplify and focus the data obtained, while data presentation made it easier for researchers to interpret information through narratives or visual forms such as tables or images. The final stage was drawing conclusions, which was carried out systematically based on data that had been analyzed in depth, so that answers to the research questions could be obtained.

To ensure data validity, triangulation techniques are used, including source triangulation, technique triangulation, and theory triangulation. Source triangulation is done by comparing data from various informants, technique triangulation by comparing results from different methods such as observation, interviews, and documentation, while theory triangulation is done by comparing findings with various relevant theories. By using these various techniques, the research is expected to have a high degree of reliability and validity of data, so that it can produce findings that are valid, objective, and in accordance with the actual conditions in the field.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. *Bawaslu's Strategy in Maintaining the Neutrality of ASN in Bone Regency*

In the Bawaslu's oversight process related to Article 4 paragraph (1) of Perbawaslu Number 6 of 2018 concerning Oversight of the Neutrality of ASN, TNI, and Polri, it is stated that election supervisors oversee the neutrality of ASN employees, TNI members, and Polri members in activities that lead to partiality towards election participants before, during, and after the campaign period.

The strategies implemented by Bawaslu to maintain civil servant neutrality, carried out by the Bone Regency Election Supervisory Agency and its staff, are as follows:

1. *Prevention*

Prevention aims to prevent election violations from occurring. The district/city Bawaslu has the task of preventing election violations and disputes over the election process, as stipulated in Article 101 paragraph 1 of Law Number 7 of 2017 concerning General Elections. Prevention is carried out by identifying potential violations that may occur during the election.

Prevention can be interpreted as proactive efforts made by Bawaslu to avoid violations in the regional election process. This prevention involves various activities aimed at increasing the understanding, awareness, and compliance of the Election Supervisory Body () with regional election regulations, as well as minimizing the risk of violations through: (Maryati & Puspita, 2025)

a. Socialization

This outreach activity was carried out using various methods, including direct meetings with civil servants in subdistricts and villages. In addition, Panwascom also distributed information materials related to civil servant neutrality rules, which were presented in a way that was easy to understand and relevant to conditions in the field. In an effort to expand the reach of information, the Bone Regency Bawaslu also collaborated with sub-district and village government agencies to disseminate further information regarding civil servant neutrality.

Vivin Sanjaya, head of the Bone Regency Bawaslu sub-division, explained that "socialization strengthens civil servants, which can reduce the number of neutrality violations in the Bone Regency. In this case, Bawaslu has invited sub-district heads, village heads, and civil servants several times to provide socialization on understanding civil servant neutrality so that the percentage of civil servant neutrality violations in Bawaslu is not too high.²

Alwi, as the Head of Bawaslu Bone Regency , explained that "In this case, Bawaslu strives to build interactive communication through open discussions and socialization to increase understanding of ASN neutrality regulations, so that those who were previously unfamiliar with the rules become more knowledgeable. The essence of the socialization is to build synergy between institutions, which is expected to be followed up with socialization and seminars in each government agency so that there will be more opportunities for discussion, which will improve understanding of civil servant neutrality in each institution."³

Erwin, an official of Timurung Village, said, " , speaking about the role of Bawaslu in ASN neutrality in Bone Regency, I think it has been quite good with the frequent socialization and issuance of appeal letters, as well as how Bawaslu has tried to engage community leaders to become participatory supervisors. all of which are systems designed to reduce the number of violations, even though in reality the community members who are expected to become participatory supervisors by Bawaslu do not function as supervisors."⁴

Umardin, as the Chairman of the PKB in Bone Regency, said, "We, as a party, have conducted political education outreach to the non-civil servant community so that political issues and election violations do not occur. However, when it comes to the neutrality of civil servants, it is

² Vivin Sanjaya (35 years old) Head of the Legal, Public Relations, Data and Information Subdivision of the Bone Regency Bawaslu, *Interview*, May 22, 2025 at the Bone Regency Bawaslu Office.

³ Alwi (53 years old), Head of the Bone Regency Bawaslu, *Interview*, May 21, 2025, at the Bone Regency Bawaslu Office .

⁴ Erwin (28 years old) Timurung Village Official, *Interview*, May 18, 2025, in Timurung Village.

beyond our authority as a party. There should be an agency or local government that works together with Bawaslu, the General Elections Commission (KPU), or an organizational institution capable of providing political education to ASN so that neutrality or pressure from superiors or any other party can be neutralized by the ASN, due to violations caused by a lack of political education."⁵

The purpose of the socialization carried out by Bawaslu and its staff is to build morale, instill values of neutrality, and raise awareness of the importance of democracy, particularly regarding the neutrality of ASN down to the village level through the village and sub-district government structures. This socialization also aims to establish tiered communication from the regency level to the lowest level. The letter of appeal for ASN neutrality in the 2024 regional elections was issued as a reminder for ASN not to get involved in practical politics that could benefit or harm certain candidate pairs. Haerul, as Panwascam, explained that the letter of appeal was delivered at every stage of the election, and specifically for ASN, data had been collected per village and distributed through PKD, including to every agency that has ASN.⁶

Preventing violations of civil servant neutrality during the election stages is done through a letter of appeal containing certain prohibitions, such as not participating in campaigns on social media, not attending candidate declarations, not taking photos with symbols of allegiance, and not using state facilities for political interests. ASN are also prohibited from declaring themselves as candidates without taking leave, becoming sources for party activities without permission, and making decisions that benefit certain candidates. Sahrul, as PKD, explained that this appeal is addressed to ASN, TNI, Polri, and other parties in accordance with the provisions of the law, and is conveyed at crucial stages such as the campaign period to ensure that all parties understand the applicable legal boundaries.⁷

b. Prevention Through Socialization Tools

Prevention through election socialization tools refers to the use of outdoor media such as stickers, billboards, banners, and posters to disseminate information about the elections, but without any campaign elements that encourage voting. The aim is to raise public awareness of the importance of neutrality in elections and not to influence voters' choices.

The Bone Regency Bawaslu has made efforts to prevent violations of ASN neutrality through the massive dissemination of information. One of the methods is by installing banners with a theme of neutrality in all 27 sub-district offices in Bone Regency. In addition, ASN neutrality banners have also been installed in village offices, sub-district offices, places of worship, and other public areas through collaboration with Panwascam in 27 sub-districts. Other efforts include installing stickers containing prohibitions on money politics in the same strategic

⁵ Umardin (40 years old), Chairman of the Bone Regency PKB, Interview, May 18, 2025, in Watampone.

⁶ Herul (33 years old) Panwascam, Interview, May 18, 2025, in Pacciro Village.

⁷ Sahrul (25 years old) PKD, Interview, May 15, 2025 in Lebbae Village.

locations. Not only outdoor media, Bawaslu also utilizes social media as a means to disseminate information about the importance of ASN neutrality, election stages, and how the public can actively participate in participatory oversight.

2. Supervision

Bawaslu supervises the compliance of all parties involved in the implementation of democratic elections, namely the presidential, legislative, and regional head elections, including supervising the neutrality of the State Civil Apparatus, the neutrality of members of the Indonesian National Army, and the neutrality of members of the Indonesian National Police. In this regard, Bawaslu has the authority to issue recommendations to the competent authorities to impose sanctions on parties who commit violations.

a. Direct Supervision in the Field

Direct supervision by Bawaslu is carried out to ensure that each stage of the election runs according to the rules and to prevent violations. The head of the Bone Regency Bawaslu, Alwi, said that supervision began with mapping vulnerable areas through a plenary meeting. Panwas and PKD in each sub-district routinely conduct patrols and attend campaign activities to ensure that there is no involvement of ASN, TNI, Polri, or other prohibited parties, as well as to prevent the emergence of SARA issues. All supervisory activities are carried out so that the implementation of the campaign remains in accordance with regulations.⁸

Bawaslu Regulation No. 13 of 2012 concerning election monitoring procedures also provides guidance to Bawaslu in order to increase public participation in election monitoring as follows: (Ajiprasetyo & Sarnawa, 2021)

- a) Actively encouraging the public to monitor elections;
- b) Providing adequate information, means, or facilities to facilitate public access to information about election monitoring; and
- c) Preparing easy means or facilities for the public to submit information, complaints, and/or reports of election violations.

Supervision of civil servant neutrality is carried out directly by the PKD and Panwas through patrols of the homes of civil servants, TNI, and Polri to ensure that no campaign materials are displayed, such as billboards, banners, or candidate stickers. During the campaign, the PKD and Panwas also monitor the presence of ASN at campaign locations, whether they are wearing campaign attire or not, and will immediately reprimand and take action if violations are found.

Adhang, as the village imam and a source in the socialization activity, said that Bawaslu had opened complaint posts in every sub-district in Bone Regency and involved the community in participatory monitoring. He emphasized the importance of the community's role in assisting Bawaslu in providing initial information on alleged violations, given the limited number of

⁸ Alwi (53 years old) Chairman of the Bone Regency Bawaslu, *Interview*, May 21, 2025 at the Bone Regency Bawaslu Office.

supervisors and the vast area under supervision. Adhang also appreciated Bawaslu's efforts in building collective awareness to create fair and democratic elections at the village level.⁹

b. Use of State or Village Facilities

The prohibition on the use of state facilities in regional head elections is based on legislation stipulating that the use of state facilities is the most common method used by regional heads during regional head elections. The authority and power vested in regional heads has great potential to be used for the interests of regional heads in winning elections. With this authority, it is very possible for regional heads to persuade, influence, and even order their subordinates to take sides and provide support for the interests of regional heads. (Ardenolis et al., 2020)

B. The View of Siyasah Syar'iyah on the Neutrality of the State Civil Apparatus in Regional Head Elections at the Bone Regency Bawaslu

The word siyasah has several meanings, namely to regulate, manage, rule, lead, make policies, govern, and politics, meaning to regulate, manage, and make policies on something political in order to achieve a goal is siyasah. Literally, the word as siyasah means: government, decision making, policy making, management, supervision, engineering, and other meanings.

Siyasah syar'iyah is a policy of the ruler whose purpose is to protect human welfare, or to uphold Allah's law, or to maintain ethics, or to spread security within the country, with what does not contradict the text, whether the text exists (explicitly) or does not exist (implicitly). The main objective of siyasah syar'iyah is to create an Islamic system of state governance and to explain that Islam desires the creation of a just political system in order to realize the welfare of humanity in all ages and in every country.

By analyzing the definitions mentioned above, the essence of Siyasah syar'iyah can be found, namely:

That Siyasah syar'iyah is related to the management and regulation of human life. This management and regulation is carried out by those in power (ulu al-amr). The purpose of this regulation is to create benefits and reject harm (jalb al-mashalih wa daf al-mafasid).

This regulation must not contradict the spirit or essence of the universal Islamic Sharia.

Based on the essence of siyasah syar'iyah, it can be concluded that the main sources of siyasah syar'iyah are the revelations of the Qur'an and al-sunnah. These two sources are the reference for those in power to create laws and regulations and regulate state affairs. (khallaf, 1977)

In terms of politics, Bawaslu is equated with the authority of al-hisbah tafwidiyah, whose duties are to handle legal matters and cases from the al-mazalim institution. The field of Siyasah tashri'iyah referred to by Bawaslu is part of fiqh dusturiyah itself, which studies and discusses the relationship between government institutions and society. Based on this study,

⁹ Adhang (29 years old) Village Imam, Interview, May 15, 2025, in Labissa Village.

the task of Bawaslu in each region () is to develop an authority program to minimize election violations so that elections can run smoothly and also to provide insight to the community so that they can participate more fairly in the political world, especially in preventing and eradicating political disputes in elections. (Manurung & Irwansyah, 2023)

Furthermore, ASN as government employees must obey and comply with the regulations made by leaders because leaders have considered everything carefully before deciding on a rule or regulation so that the regulations made by leaders do not deviate from Islamic rules and do not reduce the rights of citizens. As Allah SWT says in QS. an-Nisa`/4:59. (Ministry of Religious Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia, 2015)

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا أَطِيعُوا اللَّهَ وَأَطِيعُوا الرَّسُولَ وَأُولَى الْأَمْرِ مِنْكُمْ فَإِنْ تَنَازَعْتُمْ فِي شَيْءٍ فَرُدُّوهُ
إِلَى اللَّهِ

Translation:

O you who believe, obey Allah and obey the Messenger (Prophet Muhammad) and those in authority among you. If you disagree about something, refer it to Allah (the Qur'an) and the Messenger (his Sunnah) if you believe in Allah and the Last Day. That is better (for you) and has a better outcome (in this world and the Hereafter).

These commands encourage people to create a just and prosperous society, whose members help and assist one another, obey Allah and His Messenger, submit to those in authority, resolve disputes based on the values taught in the Qur'an and Sunnah, and follow other paths that are in accordance with Allah's will. Such is the general meaning of these verses.

The above verse relates to the role of Bawaslu in this case, which is to strive to maintain the welfare of the people through good and honest democracy, through its authority as a supervisor in enforcing the neutrality of ASN. where Bawaslu reminds or orders civil servants not to engage in any form of partisanship or practical politics. In this case, civil servants, as believers, must obey the rules issued by state leaders and Bawaslu as supervisors, as stipulated in the law.

O believers, obey Allah in His commands as stated in the Qur'an and obey His Messenger, Muhammad (peace be upon him). in all kinds of commands, both commands to do something and commands not to do something, as stated in his authentic sunnah, and also obey the commands of ulil amri, namely those who are authorized to handle your affairs, as long as they are among you, O believers, and as long as their commands do not contradict the commands of Allah or the commands of His Messenger. Therefore, if you disagree about something because you do not find clear guidance from Allah in the Qur'an- Qur'an and also not in the guidance of the Messenger in the authentic Sunnah, then refer it back to the values and spirit of Allah's words as stated in the Qur'an, and the values and spirit of the Messenger's guidance that you find in his Sunnah, if you truly believe firmly and continuously in Allah and the Hereafter. This

source of law is good and perfect, while anything else is flawed or deficient. Moreover, it yields better outcomes, both for your worldly life and your life in the Hereafter. (Shihab, 2002)

Allah SWT commands Muslims to fulfill the trust they have received. In this case, civil servants have a trust to provide quality services to the public. In addition to trust, a Muslim must also be fair, as stated in Allah's words in Surah an-Nisa' / 4:135 of the Qur'an. (Ministry of Religious Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia, 2015)

﴿يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا كُونُوا قَوَّامِينَ بِالْقِسْطِ شُهَدَاءَ لِلَّهِ وَلَوْ عَلَىٰ أَنفُسِكُمْ أَوِ الْوَالِدِينَ وَالْأَقْرَبِينَ ۚ﴾

Translation:

O you who believe, be upholders of justice and witnesses for Allah, even if it be against yourselves, your parents, or your kin. Whether he (the one burdened by the testimony) is rich or poor, Allah is more knowledgeable about the welfare of both. So do not follow your desires, seeking to deviate (from the truth). If you twist (words) or turn away (reluctant to bear witness), then indeed Allah is All-Aware of what you do.

The command in this verse uses very strong wording: "kûnû qawwâmîna bil-qisth," which indicates that justice is not just an action, but a trait that must be inherent in a believer. Similarly, ASN, as public servants, are obliged to uphold justice in carrying out their duties, including being neutral in elections as part of their professionalism.

The wording of the above verse, kûnû gawwâmîna bi al-gisthl, means to be perfect and true upholders of justice. That is, you must perfectly and attentively make the enforcement of justice an inherent trait in yourself and carry it out with great care so that it is reflected in all your outward and inward activities. Do not let anything that originates from you cloud that justice. The issue of justice is also found in the verse An-Nahl/16:90

﴿إِنَّ اللَّهَ يَأْمُرُ بِالْعَدْلِ وَالْإِحْسَانِ وَإِيتَائِي ذِي الْقُرْبَىٰ وَيَنْهَىٰ عَنِ الْفَحْشَاءِ وَالْمُنْكَرِ
وَالْبَغْيِ يَعِظُكُمْ لَعَلَّكُمْ تَذَكَّرُونَ﴾

Translation:

Indeed, Allah commands justice, kindness, and giving to relatives. He forbids immorality, wrongdoing, and hostility. He admonishes you so that you may remember. (Ministry of Religious Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia, 2015)

Indeed, Allah continuously commands all of His servants to be just in their attitudes, words, and actions, even towards themselves, and encourages them to do what is better than justice, and also to give whatever is needed and within one's means sincerely to relatives, and He, Allah, forbids all kinds of sins, especially vile acts that are condemned by religion and common sense, such as adultery and homosexuality; as well as immorality, which is things that contradict customs in accordance with religious values, and also forbids transgression, which is anything that exceeds reasonable limits. With these commands and prohibitions, He teaches

and guides you all in all aspects of virtue so that you may always remember and learn valuable lessons. (Shihab, 2002)

Humans are required to uphold justice even towards their family, parents, and themselves (QS. an-Nisa'/4:135), and even towards their enemies (QS. al-Mā'idah/5: 8). The first justice that is required is from oneself and towards oneself by putting lust and anger as prisoners who must follow the commands of reason and religion, not making them masters who direct reason and religious guidance. Because if so, he is not being fair, that is, not putting things in their proper place.

In addition to violating the applicable rules, ASNs who violate neutrality have also violated the oath they have taken as stipulated in Law No. 43 of 1999 concerning Amendments to Law No. 8 of 1974 concerning Civil Service Principles contained in Article 26 paragraph (1) In principle, a civil servant candidate who has passed the selection process before being inaugurated as a civil servant will take an oath of office. The oath taken by civil servants is done by bringing a holy book according to their respective religions and accompanied by religious leaders according to their respective religions. For Muslims, the oath reads, "By Allah, I swear/promise: that I, to be appointed as a civil servant, will be loyal and fully obedient to Pancasila, the 1945 Constitution, the State and the Government, and that by violating the principle of ASN neutrality, I have violated the law and also religion. As stated in Surah Ali Imran/ 3:77.

إِنَّ الَّذِينَ يَشْتَرُونَ بِعَهْدِ اللَّهِ وَأَيْمَانِهِمْ ثَمَنًا قَلِيلًا أُولَٰئِكَ لَا خَلَاقَ لَهُمْ فِي الْآخِرَةِ وَلَا يُكَلِّمُهُمُ اللَّهُ وَلَا يَنْظُرُ

Translation:

Indeed, those who trade the covenant of Allah and their oaths for a small price, they will have no share in the Hereafter, Allah will not speak to them, nor will He look at them on the Day of Resurrection, nor will He purify them. For them is a painful punishment. (Ministry of Religious Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia, 2015)

The above verse explains how important it is for believers who have taken an oath to uphold it, and likewise, civil servants must have strong integrity as public servants who have been sworn in using the holy book, so that civil servants do not easily trade their oaths or exchange them for worldly positions or because of pressure or intervention during elections. Looking at the verse above, we can see how detrimental it is for a believer to violate their oath, and likewise, how detrimental it is for a civil servant to violate the rules of civil servant neutrality. This is because civil servants have deliberately or unintentionally violated their oath as civil servants and have betrayed their country and religion.

Legally, the oath taken by civil servants is mandatory. The oath taken by civil servants is not only declared before the authorized government, but it is also a commitment to Allah SWT. If all civil servants are Muslims, then civil servants should obey ulil amri and carry out their oath.

Do not say that their attitude toward you is good or that they please you. They only please you with their mouths, that is, with their words, while their hearts are unwilling to please you and even intend to harm you. Very few of them are motivated by loyalty to fulfill the agreement, and most of them are wicked people who have become ingrained and cultured in their wickedness, so that they do not keep their agreements. Because of this wickedness, they exchange the verses of Allah, the guidance and proof of truth presented by the Messenger, especially the Qur'an, for a price that, no matter how much it is, is still of little value, even though if they follow it they will receive countless divine blessings that are priceless. Thus, they prevent themselves and anyone else from the path of Allah. Indeed, what they persistently do is truly evil. (Shihab, 2002)

From Abu Hurairah, that the Prophet SAW said:

آيَةُ الْمُنَافِقِ ثَلَاثٌ إِذَا حَدَّثَ كَذَبَ وَإِذَا وَعَدَ أَخْلَفَ وَإِذَا أُؤْتِمِنَ خَانَ.

Translation:

"The signs of a hypocrite are three: when he speaks, he lies; when he makes a promise, he breaks it; and when he is entrusted with something, he betrays that trust" (H.R. Al-Bukhari)

In general elections, civil servants must adhere to the principle of neutrality, whereby they do not take sides with any of the candidates running for regional leadership.

In the context of elections, the neutrality of ASN is a tangible form of the implementation of the principle of siyasah syar'iyah (Islamic political science) which is based on justice. The obedience of ASN to ulil amri (those in authority) and Bawaslu (Election Supervisory Agency) regulations is not only a constitutional obligation, but also part of the implementation of the mandate and oath that has been declared before Allah SWT.

Therefore, civil servants who are believers must maintain neutrality, uphold justice, and set an example in national and state life. Violating the neutrality of the state () means violating the oath, undermining justice, and betraying the trust of the people and religion.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion, the following conclusions can be drawn: The first strategy implemented by Bawaslu in maintaining the neutrality of ASN is prevention, which is a proactive effort carried out by Bawaslu to avoid violations in the regional election process involving various activities, including socialization, distribution of appeal letters, and prevention through social media. The second strategy is supervision, which involves direct supervision in the field and supervision of the use of state or village facilities.

Violations of ASN neutrality in Bone Regency in 2024 from a syar'iyah political perspective In this case, ASN has violated the principle of justice in syar'iyah politics, which can cause harm to themselves and the community. In addition, ASN has violated the law and reneged on their oath, which is strictly prohibited in Islam because taking an oath is an obligatory law. The penalty for violators and those who renege on their oath is sin.

RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

In this case, the Bone Regency Election Supervisory Agency (Bawaslu) is expected to be more active in disseminating information on ASN neutrality to lower levels by collaborating with local government agencies. This is because Bawaslu only disseminates information on ASN neutrality to ASN who hold positions or offices such as sub-district heads and village heads or field heads, because in general, lower-level ASN are less familiar with the rules of ASN neutrality.

Political ethics in syar'iyah politics can be used as a reference in maintaining ASN neutrality by the government, Bawaslu, and ASN themselves. In addition, the government and Bawaslu need to increase transparency in the process of monitoring and enforcing laws related to ASN neutrality. Providing clear and detailed reports on actions taken against violations of neutrality and the results of monitoring will increase accountability and public trust in the election process. This openness is important to ensure that all actions are in accordance with the principles of justice and applicable laws.

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